

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF PRIMITIVE SOCIETY IN JAMBI, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This study aims to (1) reveal the phenomenon of physical activity of primitive society in their daily life, (2) understand which physical activities have the element to improve physical performance, (3) understand which physical activities have the element of motor skills. The subject of the study is physical activity conducted by primitive society of *Suku Anak Dalam* in Jambi, Sumatera, Indonesia. This study uses descriptive qualitative method with phenomenology approach. Level of confidence is tested by using data triangulation from the informants who are considered to understand the primitive society *Suku Anak Dalam's* life structure. The analysis in this study is conducted within five stages, which are: (1) data reduction, (2) data display, (3) conclusion drawing, (4) validity result improvement and (5) narrative analysis result. The result of study shows that: (1) there is physical activity conducted by *Suku Anak Dalam* people as part of survival activity in the jungle, (2) there is physical activity which has the element of physical performance, (3) there is physical activity which has the element of motor skills.

Keywords: physical activity, primitive society, *Suku Anak Dalam*, physical performance, motor skills

1. Introduction

In this era, there are primitive societies which hunt and gather foods as a living. Usually primitive societies still maintain their ancestral traditions, both in the activity of looking for food or in customs. For primitive societies, maintaining and preserving the cultural

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tradition is an obligation that must be done, so that parents are obliged to teach the gospel to children or descendants of their ancestors so preservation continues.

The categorization and classification of elements of cultivation according to Alo Liliweri (2014: 432), type of society based on the viewpoint of ecological-evolutionary theory states "*one; hunter and food gatherers (12000-8000 SM), two; horticultural society (8000-3000 SM), three; agricultural society (3000-1800 SM), four; industrial society (1800-now)*". In the above explanation, it can be classified that primitive tribe societies are included in the category of hunters and food gatherers that still remain in indigenous group of *Suku Anak Dalam* in the Forest of Bukit Dua Belas National Park, Jambi Indonesia.

On the physical activity of primitive societies, there is something unique to reveal. It can be seen from the activities of physical activity of primitive society in the process of gathering food to be able to live in the jungle, as well as physical activity done at the time of hunters and gatherers who have an element in shaping the physical abilities and skills of individual motion.

Based on Adi Prasetijo (2011: 192) "*the life of Suku Anak Dalam people who live in the forest meet the basic needs independently of the results of forest and forest activities. They can meet the needs of staple foods such as cassava by searching the forest. For protein, they obtain them from hunting and fishing. To meet needs such as cigarettes, clothing, and fabrics they obtain them from selling the yield of forest resources*". Hunting and gathering activities are still taking place in public life of *Suku Anak Dalam* in Bukit Dua Belas National Park, Jambi, Indonesia.

In general, the process of physical activity by individuals indirectly affects the body condition of the doer. As in the ability of the immune system, which are increased and better motor skills obtained from movements done repeatedly.

Endurance capacity is biomotor components that are needed in physical activity. And one of the most important components of physical fitness. Endurance is also understood as durability time which means the length of a person to be able to keep on working or endure the intensity of fatigue. Endurance is the ability to do the job in a relatively long time.

While the movement skill is the ability of motion that can be done by humans in performing activities that require special skills which are trained or obtained from the motion experience gained from physical activity. Movement skill is the ability to perform a task motion optimally according to his ability. Skill motion on each person is different, there are several factors that affect the skill such as levels of age and experience of motion.

Based on the introduction which is stated previously, the aims of the study concluded in this study are to: (1) reveal the phenomenon of physical activity of primitive society

in daily life, (2) describe the kinds of physical activity that has an element of improving physical ability, (3) describe the kinds of physical activity that has an element of movement skills.

2. Research Method

This study used descriptive qualitative method with phenomenological hermeneutic approach. The study contained three stages. The first stage was the collection of data that collect the data on the location of the study through observation, interview, and documentation. The second stage was the analysis of the implementation of data. The early implementation of the initial data analysis, verification, enrichment and deepening of the data and developed in the form of data presentation and followed by formulating a conclusion. The third stage was the preparation of the study, in this stage of the study; the report validity was tested and discuss the reports that have been prepared by some experts and then revises the report and write the final report of the study.

This research was conducted in Bukit Dua Belas National Park in Jambi Province, Sumatra, Indonesia. Source of data in the early stages of entering the location of the study, the writer chose informants who know and understand the living condition of *Suku Anak Dalam* which is accompanied by a guide of *Suku Anak Dalam* from the Ministry of Social Affairs. Research subject in this study is *Suku Anak Dalam* society.

The writer used some tools to help in data collection and data analysis which were field notes, a voice recorder, a video recorder, and a camera. The technique of collecting data tends to be participant observation, in depth interview and documentation. While the analysis of the data used triangulation techniques including data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing / verification.

Data collection techniques included observation, interviews, literature review, and documentation. Meanwhile, in order to establish the validity of the data, it used triangulation techniques. The data were then analyzed using three techniques, which were: flow models, interactive models and analysis domain. Data were obtained from various sources; interviews and field notes. Data analysis performed in this study was: (1) data reduction, (2) data, (3) conclusion, (4) increase of the validity of the results, and (5) narrative analysis.

3. Result and Discussion

This study uses interview and observation system which is obtained from the field, the object of the study is *Suku Anak Dalam* society. In the early stages of research on

November-December 2016, the initial observation on the subject that has been determined, the observed physical activity conducted by *Suku Anak Dalam* people when doing the hunting and gathering activities. In this chapter, the writer will present the results that have been obtained from interviews with informants through direct observation, the writer can analyze the physical activity of *Suku Anak Dalam* people, the writer is able to analyze the physical activity which has an element of improving physical ability and movement skills. With the process of interviews conducted by the informant, the writer could analyze things which appear and disclosed by the informant with descriptive procedures including written or oral based on physical activity of *Suku Anak Dalam* society. The result of the analysis which is obtained by in-depth interviews, observation and documentation are as follows:

3.1 Physical Activity Phenomenon in *Suku Anak Dalam* Society

The house type of *Suku Anak Dalam* society has the form of hut in order to enable them to move, the government has built several houses for some groups of *Suku Anak Dalam* although there are a few empty houses because many of those who do *melangun* (the process of leaving the original settlement to eliminate the grief if there are relatives who died) and the house is left empty.

The entire living source of *Suku Anak Dalam* people lies in the forest with two activities; hunting and gathering. Hunting boars, deers, and elks are part of life for *Suku Anak Dalam* people by using tools such as spears, snares and guns. Hunting is done individually or in teams of two to five people. Usually they look for hiding places of the animal shelter. If the hunting target appears, then they are for the next hunt.

Gathering foods is the activity of looking for extra foods and other vegetations. In addition to searching for tubers and fruits, *Suku Anak Dalam* people are also looking for some other forest materials, such as; honey, rattan, medicinal plants, and firewood. They also look for fish in the river using fish spears, traps (*bubu*), shoot the fish, and noodling (*ngakop*).

Physical activity is the lifestyle of the *Suku Anak Dalam* people as a form of survival in order to survive in the jungle. The life pattern of *Suku Anak Dalam* people cannot be separated from physical activity, because any activity undertaken is always in direct contact with the body. This is due to physical activity in the daily life of *Suku Anak Dalam* including; hunting, fishing and gathering is the way of gathering food.

Based on the above explanation, it can be seen that some physical activity conducted by a group of primitive society in hunting, are: pike activity, fishing activity, activity in gathering food and the activity of collecting some materials in the woods.

3.2 Physical Activity which Has the Element of Increasing Physical Performance

Physical activity done by *Suku Anak Dalam* people give the effect for limb movement of the doer that is formed from physical activity that they do everyday so that they are unaware that these activities affect the ability of the immune system. The following is a physical activity or physical activity that has elements in improving physical abilities in *Suku Anak Dalam* people, which are: hunting with spears, hunting with rifle, gathering food and collecting some materials from the woods.

3.2.1 Hunting Activity

These activities do not depend on time, instead it depends on the individual when the hunting activities would be done, and the activity can be done in the morning, afternoon, during the day or night. In hunting activities usually the hunters have to walk deep into the jungle, they have to run after prey animals, and sometimes they must swim when the target prey is on the other side of the river. It is indirectly and unconsciously forming endurance and with erratic weather that boost the immune system of the skin that hence will hold hot or cold weather.

Besides, the far trip of hunting also affects one's physical endurance; the road taken by the time of hunting is sometimes up and down because of the geography of where *Suku Anak Dalam* people live inside the Taman Nasional Dua Belas jungle which has hilly ground contour. As stated by Ottawa (1998: 7) "*Strength activities help your muscles and bones stay strong, improve your posture and help to prevent diseases like osteoporosis. Strength activities are those that make you work your muscles against some kind of resistance, like when you push or pull hard to open a heavy door*". As stated by Ottawa that strenuous activity affects the formation of muscles and bones strong. We can know that hunting activity is considered as heavy work, in the process of hunting the hunter must do some settings in the process of hunting like; walking, running, swimming and bringing the quarry.

3.2.2 Gathering Activity or Collecting Foods and Material in the Jungle

Gathering foods is the process of finding foods and forest types of material such as firewood for cooking and rattan which is commonly used by *Suku Anak Dalam* people as ambung or bags made from rattan to help them in carrying goods. These activities are included into heavy work because a single person may carry 50 kg to 75 kg, the goods carried are varied such as tubers, fruits, rattan and firewoods. Physical activity is unwittingly forming muscle and bone strength so that it is rarely found a member of *Suku Anak Dalam* who is obese and almost every individual in *Suku Anak Dalam* society has the ideal muscular body shape.

3.3 Physical Activity which Has the Element of Motor Skills

Physical activity that they do, there is a lot of activities that affect the ability of the movement skills of *Suku Anak Dalam* people. From the movement skills that are subtle and tough. This capability is owned by the people of *Suku Anak Dalam* as the cultural traditions of physical activity they do every day and repeatedly so that this ability continues to stick to each individual.

Good physical ability and movement skills make *Suku Anak Dalam* people able to survive the tough life. With physical abilities and movement skills obtained since child, *Suku Anak Dalam* people form a strong and skilled human from the compulsion to do to be able to continue to live with the family.

With the diversified activities and tools used in *Suku Anak Dalam* daily activities, there are some elements of physical activity that has an element of movement skills. The following is a physical activity that has elements of motor skills:

3.3.1 Piking Activity

Piking activity is conducted during hunting period in the woods. To use the pike, it requires good motor skills with the right technique so that the throw can hit the target. Piking activity requires the combination of accuracy, speed, technique, and strength to do the throw.

The limbs used in the process of piking are arms and legs including muscles like hand muscles as the spring used to throw, finger muscles to clamp the pike, chest muscles and arm muscles as the thrust to do the throw and leg muscles used as the stance during the pike throw, with the help eyes coordination to see the target and the hand as the tool when throwing.

Piking skill is taught by *Suku Anak Dalam* people when the children are able to walk. This is done by the parents so that their children can look for their own food in the future. The technique that is learned uses vision method, which is to ask their children to go with the parents when hunting and see by themselves how their parents use and throw the pike correctly to hit the target.

Motor skills in piking use hard motion which means the motion done using large muscles. Regarding this, the learning process is done continuously and it keeps developing until they master the piking activity.

3.3.2 Shooting Activity

Shooting using guns is one of the tools used by *Suku Anak Dalam* people to hunt. This tool is used to hunt big animals such as deer and boar. Due to acculturation from externals of *Suku Anak Dalam* people, they start using modern tools to hunt, using guns not only help them to hunt easier, but also avoid the risks of using pike, because using

pike has a lot of risks, such as getting rammed by boars even there are some people who die because they get rammed by a big boar. Guns also help them avoid the risks although it comes with its own risks like aiming the wrong target and other people may get shot.

Teaching to shoot is similar to the method of teaching children to hunt using vision method, which is seeing by their own eyes how the technique is conducted by the parents. The muscle used to shoot is the small muscle that works when the finger pull the trigger of the guns.

The skill used to shoot requires agility and skill to shoot. This skill needs to be honed by keep doing the activity with the parents when hunting and sometimes the parents ask their children to try to shoot the target animals. This activity is continuously done so they grow the feeling when shooting the target and finally they can hit the target.

It is common for parents ask their children to go hunting together using guns in the age of 14 or older. It is based on the consideration of *Suku Anak Dalam* people that using guns should require standard body height and strong arm to endure the impact of gun shooting. The reason they have standard height is because the tip of the gun should be pointed down to the ground to avoid shooting other people coincidentally.

3.3.3 Catching Fish Activity

Ngakop or noodling is the activity of fish catching done by *Suku Anak Dalam* people with bare hands and this activity are done when the river is at ebb tide. This activity is done by walking across the river and the fish caught with bare hands.

The fish catching activity requires good motor skills. *Ngakop* activity requires the coordination of speed, strength, and good accuracy. If it is not done in high speed, the target will run away and the grip should also be strong so that the fish does not get away *Ngakop* activity requires hard motion which requires motion using large muscles such as arm muscle and strong grip from finger muscle. *Ngakop* skill is obtained by the children of *Suku Anak Dalam* through self-taught learning, which means they only see other people do *ngakop*. This activity is done to help the parents gather foods.

3.3.4 Catching Snakes Activity

Snake catching activity is done by *Suku Anak Dalam* people using bare hands. This activity requires good motor skills, first; speed is necessary when catching snakes, second; accuracy is necessary to catch snake head because the snake moves aggressively in dangerous situation, hence accuracy is needed to catch snake head, three; the hand strength to grip is necessary to avoid snake attack in the catching process.

Snake catching activity is done with appropriate measure of snake size, when there is a big snake it requires two or three people to catch it to avoid the twist of the snake. And the snake target is commonly python or snake in paddy field. They can sell the snake skin and the snake meat can be used as food material for *Suku Anak Dalam* people.

4. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data from the previous discussion, it can be acquired some conclusions as follow:

- a) There is a phenomenon of physical activity in the life of *Suku Anak Dalam* primitive society which still continues to happen until today as to survive in the forest. The physical activities are; hunting using pike, guns, and bare hands. The activity of catching fish, such as; *ngakob* or noodling (catching fish using bare hands). The activity of gathering foods and material from the forest such as; tubers, honey, fruits, rattan, and firewood.
- b) In the series of activity that they do, there are several physical activities that has an element of physical ability increase such as the activity of hunting and gathering food and material in the forest. This can be seen from the heavy work they do in their daily life in order to survive and almost all of *Suku Anak Dalam* people have ideal muscular body.
- c) The physical activity done by *Suku Anak Dalam* people has the element of motor skills such as the hunting process as well as catching fish. In terms of motor skills of *Suku Anak Dalam* people, it can be seen from the technique used to pike, shoot, catch fish and snake using bare hands.
- d) The activity of piking has similar motion with javelin throw. The javelin grip technique generally uses American and Finland technique style. The way the American grips is by holding the javelin behind the cord with the index finger goes around behind the cord and the thumb push the other side, while the other fingers also go around the body of the javelin loosely. Finland style is by holding the javelin behind the cord with middle finger and thumb, while index finger holds in the body and a little askew to an appropriate direction; the other fingers also hold the body of the javelin loosely. The way *Suku Anak Dalam* people hold the body of the pike by clamping using thumb and the distal phalanx to clamp the pike.

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